

Supporting primary school teachers to include a child who is visually impaired in the Primary PE lesson – ‘Exploring the Methodology’

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The paper presents an outline of the methodological approach used to examine supports which are needed by teachers to include a child who is visually impaired (VI) in the Primary Physical Education (PE) lesson. There are approximately 2,598 (NCBI, 2023) children who are VI currently in Irish primary schools. Previous research in this areas indicates that children who are VI exhibit lower levels of motor competence (Lieberman *et al.*, 2014; Meier, Höger and Giese, 2023). There is limited research however, in relation to how teachers can be supported to meaningfully include children who are VI in PE lessons. Within the Irish context, it is noteworthy that there is scarce evidence regarding how children with additional needs (AN) are included in PE lessons (Marron *et al.*, 2023), despite this being a focus of discussion internationally. This current research study seeks to address this knowledge and practice gap. This paper establishes the methodological approach of semi-structured interviews which was employed to examine the lived experiences of teachers in Ireland who have taught PE to children who are VI in the mainstream class setting. The method of thematic analysis used to examine the findings of this research study is explored in detail. Participant recruitment, limitations and challenges faced by the researcher are discussed alongside ethical considerations. This paper concludes with an overview of the importance of qualitative research and the value of employing semi-structured interviews as a methodological approach.

Key Words: Inclusive Pedagogy, Inclusion, Visual Impairment (VI), Mainstream Primary School, Physical Education (PE), Supporting teachers

Highlights

- There is limited research in relation to how teachers can be supported to meaningfully include children who are VI in PE lessons, particularly in the Irish context
- A qualitative research methodology of semi-structured interviews was employed to understand the lived experiences of teachers teaching PE to children who are VI in Irish mainstream primary schools
- The method of Thematic Analysis (TA) (Braun and Clarke, 2006) was used to analyse the data set

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Introduction

There is a considerable amount of research which highlights the fact that children with a visually impairment (VI) currently exhibit lower levels of motor competence (Lieberman *et al.*, 2014), demonstrate motor development delays (Houwen *et al.*, 2010; Wagner, Haibach and Lieberman, 2013) and are significantly less active (Haegele and Porretta, 2015; Brian *et al.*, 2019) in comparison to their sighted peers. Children who are VI more commonly report encountering barriers to engagement with physical activity (PA). These include: limited access to adapted sports and activities (Kirk, Haegele and Zhu, 2023), a scarcity of opportunities and interventions (Lieberman, Robinson and Rollheiser, 2006; Haegele and Porretta, 2015), and a shortage of available practice locations (Tanure Alves, Haegele and Duarte, 2018). In some cases, this can result in these children not participating in the PE lesson at all (Stuart, Lieberman and Hand, 2006). At present, there is a perceived misconception that children who are VI are unable to reach the same levels of PA as their sighted peers (Alfrey and Jeanes, 2023), however, when afforded the proper tools to partake, learn and participate (Stuart, Lieberman and Hand, 2006; Lieberman *et al.*, 2019), children who are VI have the potential to reach the same level of participation as their sighted peers (Lieberman, Robinson and Rollheiser, 2006; Lieberman *et al.*, 2019).

Within the Irish context, it is notable that there is limited evidence regarding how children with additional needs (AN) are included in PE lessons (Marron *et al.*, 2023), despite this being a focus of discussion internationally. A research study conducted in Ireland by Flynn *et al.* (2024) found that children who are blind or visually impaired (BVI) are less active than their sighted peers, and spend less time in PE class. Furthermore, there is limited research in relation to how teachers can be supported to meaningfully include children who are VI in PE lessons, highlighting a particular gap in the literature in this area within the Irish context. This research study sought to address this gap by gathering the lived experiences of teachers in Ireland who have taught PE to children who are VI in the mainstream class setting.

This article will outline the methodological approach employed for this qualitative research study.

Methods

A qualitative research approach was adopted to understand the lived experiences of teachers teaching PE to children who are VI in Irish mainstream primary schools. As stated by Flick (2018), “qualitative research is ... based on specific attitudes, of openness towards

who and what is studied, of flexibility in approaching a field and moving in it, of understanding a subject's or a field's structure rather than projecting a structure into what is studied" (p. 16). Three research questions were formulated and refined upon completion of the literature review for this study.

1. What is the practice, knowledge and understanding of primary teachers as they teach children who are visually impaired physical education within the mainstream primary school?
2. What are the successes and challenges experiences by primary teachers when teaching physical education to children who are visually impaired within the mainstream primary school?
3. What are the supports that children who are visually impaired and their teachers require to enhance the learning experience of these children?

Semi-structured interviews were chosen as the sole methodology for this research study. To ensure that data was accurately gathered and represented, an interview schedule was created using Kvale's (1996) seven stages of an interview investigation. The interview schedule consisted of a range of open-ended questions spanning three main foci:

1. General teaching experience
2. Teaching PE and teaching PE to children who are BVI
3. Initial Teacher Education (ITE) and Continuous Professional Development (CPD)

Time was spent planning and redrafting the interview schedule to create a high quality set of interview questions. A series of prompts were included for each question in the interview schedule. Prompts encourage participants to open up and to speak at length and provide more detail about the specific focus of the interview question asked (Braun and Clarke, 2013). The use of semi-structured interviews allowed the researcher to alter the questions slightly based on the knowledge and experiences of the participant being interviewed, allowing each interview to be unique (Rubin, 2005). A pilot interview was also conducted before interviewing participants for this research project. The pilot interview provided an opportunity to identify unclear questions that required amendments and redrafting.

Mainstream teachers who were teaching or had taught a child who is VI were invited to participate in this research study. An email recruiting participants was sent to 3,089 schools using the Department of Education and Youth database. An advertisement calling for participants in this research project was also sent by Vision Sport Ireland to its member database via email. The call for participants garnered responses from a diverse group of participants. A total of eleven semi-structured qualitative interviews were conducted. Three

teachers interviewed were Special Education Teachers (SET) and 8 teachers were mainstream class teachers, with one teacher working as the Special Educational Needs Coordinator (SENCO) in her school.

Having expressed an interest in taking part in an interview for the research project, participants were sent an email which contained the participation information sheet which included an overview of the research project explaining why the research was being conducted, and information regarding the protection and storage of personal information. The interview schedule containing the questions for the interview was also attached in the email so that the participants could familiarise themselves with the questions in advance of the interview.

The interviews with participants were conducted over the internet using the video calling software, Zoom. Since the COVID-19 pandemic, virtual interviews have become more prominent due to their convenience and accessibility for participants (Braun and Clarke, 2013). Conducting interviews via the online platform Zoom, allowed a greater diversity in the sample selection as interviews with participants could be conducted with relative ease. Research has suggested that online interviews do not produce interviews of a lower quality when compared to interviews conducted in person (Jenner and Myers, 2019). A transcript of each interview was generated by Zoom following each interview. A key element of transcriptions is the documentation of “what is said and who is speaking” (Braun, 2013). These transcripts were reviewed thoroughly to ensure that the software had appropriately transcribed the conversations during the interview. Each transcript was approximately 14 pages in length with a total of 8,000 words in each interview, with each interview lasting approximately 45 minutes.

Ethical Considerations

The nature of qualitative data creates complex ethical issues due to the personal style of this type of research. The researcher was guided by the guidelines provided by the Research Ethics Committee (REC) in DCU. Ethical Approval for the research project was applied for in March 2024 and was granted in June 2024. Ethical considerations relevant to this research project are outlined below, and include anonymity, autonomy, and risk assessment.

Anonymity

Anonymity involves the removal of “any means of identification” (Cohen, 2018, p. 129). The protection of anonymity for any participant of a research study is critically important but can be problematic given the nature of qualitative research (Flick, 2018b). Although a researcher cannot promise complete anonymity when conducting face-to-face interviews via an online platform, confidentiality can be assured (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2011). Pseudonyms were used for the purpose of preserving anonymity of the participants. It must be noted that although this requires the information to be altered in some form, this does not make any major changes to the meaning of the data collected (Kvale, 1996). It is argued by James and Busher (2007) that within the field of online research, it is very difficult to ensure the anonymity and confidentiality of participants especially when emails are being used for correspondence between the researcher and participants. Therefore, it was necessary to explain to participants that the data collected is subject to legal limitations as part of the guidelines provided by the Data Protection Unit, DCU.

Autonomy

All participants of this research project were informed about the aims of this study and were afforded the opportunity to choose freely whether or not to participate (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2011). A participant information sheet, plain language statement and an informed consent form were created and approved as part of the ethics approval form. Following interest from the participants in partaking in this study, the plain language statement and informed consent form, along with the interview schedule, were sent to participants. Seeking informed consent as part of a research project is essential as this outlines the possible risks and benefits to the participant in engaging in the research project as well as outlining the overall purpose of the investigation (Kvale, 2007). These documents were sent to ensure that the participants understood the aims and implications of partaking in the research. Participants were informed that they could withdraw from the study at any point during the research (Kvale, 2007) without repercussions and were reminded that all participation in the research project was completely voluntary (Lochmiller, 2017). The informed consent form was obtained from each participant prior to commencing the research.

Risk assessment

“A major ethical dilemma is that which requires researchers to strike a balance between the demands placed on them as professional scientists in pursuit of truth, and their subjects’ rights and values potentially threatened by research” (Cohen, 2018, p. 232). Informing participants about the potential risks of partaking in a research study is an essential

section of the informed consent form (Lochmiller, 2017). Therefore, participants were informed that the risk of participating in the research project was low, as it involved no greater risk than those encountered in everyday life when sharing opinions in a professional context. Although the level of risk associated with participating in the research project was low, researchers must consider both the potential risks and benefits for participants involved in any study. A number of direct benefits for participants of this research project were identified and noted in the participant information form. These benefits include:

1. Participants of this study will be provided with sample resources and exemplars to support and enhance their teaching of PE to children who are VI.
2. Teachers also have the opportunity to seek support and advice about how they might enhance the experiences for a child who is VI in their PE lesson.

It is essential that the guidelines surrounding data protection as outlined in the ethics application form are strictly adhered to for ethical reasons. All data collected on mobile devices for the purposes of this research project was protected with a strong password. All data which was stored on a mobile device was removed from these devices as soon as it was practical and stored securely in a DCU Google Drive account. All paper based data was held securely in locked cabinets in DCU, with access restricted to the named researchers, as noted on the DCU ethics application form. Participants of the research project were made aware that only the two supervisors and the researcher had access to the data collected and that all data would be destroyed on completion of the academic studies of the researcher.

Analysis

With regards to qualitative data, “data collection and data analysis go hand in hand” (Taylor, 2016, p. 189). The method of Thematic Analysis (TA) was chosen to carry out analysis of the data contained within this research project. TA is a method for “identifying, analysing and reporting patterns (themes) within data” (Braun and Clarke, 2006, p. 79). TA is a very appropriate method for analysing data for those who are embarking on their study of qualitative research (Braun and Clarke, 2013), which is accessible to researchers who have little or no experience of engaging in qualitative research (Braun and Clarke, 2006). A particular strength of TA is the flexibility of this method which can be used to answer almost any research question and which can be used to analyse virtually any form of data (Braun and Clarke, 2013). The method of TA also allows researchers to develop basic coding skills as well as data-handling techniques (Braun and Clarke, 2013).

Although there are many strengths associated with the method of TA (Braun and Clarke, 2013), there are a series of limitations associated with it also. TA can result in a failure to analyse the data, using the data collection questions as themes, or a weak or unconvincing analysis of the data (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Failure to analyse the data collected can result in sections of extracts being linked together with no analytic narrative. Regarding questions used in data collection, this suggests that no analysis of the data has been conducted to produce themes across the entire data set (Braun and Clarke, 2006). An inadequate analysis of the data can result in overlap between themes, with themes becoming internally incoherent and inconsistent (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

The TA of the data comprised of six steps as outlined below:

Familiarisation

Transcription of the data was orthographically completed within two months of the interviews taking place. These transcripts of the interviews were generated using the online platform, Zoom, and were reviewed extensively to ensure the transcription had been completed correctly.

Immersion in the data then followed. This requires gaining a deep understanding of the knowledge within the dataset gathered and noticing elements of the data which might be relevant to the research questions (Braun, 2013). Notes were also taken based on what was spoken about during the various interviews, allowing the researcher to identify questions which they had during the interview.

Coding

Following the editing and revision of the transcriptions created by Zoom, the process of rigorous coding began. Braun and Clarke (2013) state that coding “involves systematically working through each data item and [the] entire dataset” (p. 60). Coding allows the data gathered to be categorised so that a plan of thematic ideas can be established (Gibbs, 2007). A manual coding approach was taken to allow the researcher to become fully immersed in the dataset collected. Each word, phrase, sentence and paragraph were examined closely with specific attention. Any words which were found to be relevant when examining the data were highlighted with a different coloured highlighter and given a code name.

The application of the manual coding process resulted in the creation of 16 clusters of codes (see Table 1 overleaf).

Table 1: Code clusters

Strategies for teaching PE to children who are VI	Support from professionals in school (SNA)	Facilities & Equipment	Current support from external professionals
General strategies for teaching children who are VI	Importance of inclusion	Initial Teacher Education (ITE)	Knowledge of teachers and support provided
Teacher dispositions	Difference in VI	Safety concerns	Assistive technology (AT) provision for children who are VI
Additional support from professionals in school	Additional support from external professionals	Further supports wanted by teachers	Continuous Professional Development (CPD)

The data was coded and each excerpt from the transcript was assigned a code. This allowed for a deeper analysis of the data gathered for the creation of suitable themes. While frequency of certain codes was noted, the process of manual coding allowed for all relevant elements of the data captured to be examined and analysed in relation to addressing the research questions.

Searching for themes

An in-depth review of the codes and cluster of codes was conducted to search for patterns across the codes developed. Reviewing the codes created allowed overlaps between codes to appear. These overlaps and similarities between codes led to the emergence of candidate themes.

Reviewing themes

A review of the initial themes and their relative subthemes was conducted. The data and the relevant codes were reviewed. This allowed the researcher to once again immerse themselves in the dataset and move away from examining codes in isolation. This allows for analysis of the data, eliminating inaccurate recall, loss of context and failure to recall the full scope of the dataset (Braun and Clarke, 2022).

Defining and naming themes

Following a review of the data and the initial themes, developing a name for each of the themes was addressed. The themes required a name which would be concise, catchy and

informative (Braun and Clarke, 2022). It was important that the names of these themes did not misrepresent the data analysis by creating topic summaries rather than true thematic representations. The following three theme names were developed upon completion of the review: 1) The landscape for PE for children who are VI; 2) Influences on teachers' practice, knowledge and understanding of teaching children who are VI and; 3) Supports for inclusion in PE identified by teachers.

Challenges

An email seeking participants for this research project was sent in late September 2024. The timing of this email may not have been the most appropriate, as teachers were settling into a new school year, many with a new group of students. As a result, some of the teachers interviewed had not spent sufficient time working with the child who is VI, which was reflected in their responses to the interview questions. The timing of the email may have contributed to the limited participation in the research project, as September is an extremely busy month for schools across the country. As a result, the email had to be recirculated through the Department of Education and Youth database in October 2024. Vision Sport Ireland also contacted schools in an effort to recruit additional participants.

Limitations

In relation to the methodology of semi-structured interviews employed, a level of consistency can be difficult to achieve across all interviews as the questions which are asked and data which is collected is dependent on the participants themselves (Denscombe, 2014). Due to the nature of the data collected from semi-structured interviews, this data is not pre-coded and therefore the coding of this data can be a time consuming process which can only begin after the data has been collected (Denscombe, 2014). Furthermore, it is important to note that, although the validity of the data can be ensured at the data entry stage, the data collected is dependent on what people say rather than their actual actions and what they do (Denscombe, 2014). Therefore, the use of semi-structured interviews can be considered a 'reactive' method of data collection, as participants may provide information that is not entirely accurate or truthful (Denscombe, 2021).

Conclusions

This article outlined the qualitative methodology of semi-structured interviews which was effectively employed to examine and understand the lived experiences of teachers teaching PE to children who are VI in Irish mainstream primary schools. The use of qualitative research in this setting proved to be beneficial as it allowed the researcher to talk directly to the participants, understand their experiences and gather multiple perspectives on the topic (Creswell, 2018). Qualitative research allowed for an understanding of the context and situations which primary school teachers find themselves in as they include children who are VI in primary PE lessons (Creswell, 2018).

Semi-structured interviews provided a rich data set for examining the subject of this research study. Comments made by teachers could be probed to further understand the participants' responses to the questions asked (Denscombe, 2021). It also allowed participants to expand on topics that were important to them. The flexible structure of semi-structured interviews allowed the researcher to adjust the questions based on participants' responses. The interview scenario also allowed participants to speak freely about the subject of this research project, while the researcher listened attentively and without judgment.

Looking forward, a Design-Based Research (Brown, 1992) methodology could be employed to examine the subject of this study in greater detail in the future. This methodology involves four stages; designing supports to address a learning problem, implementing these supports in a classroom situation with constant revision where necessary, evaluating the supports and examining student learning, and finally, reflecting on and critiquing these supports and the implementation process. This approach would allow the researcher to design supports for teachers, enabling them to implement these resources in their classrooms while also reviewing and refining them for broader dissemination to other teachers in the future. This would facilitate a cyclical process of support for teachers.

This paper in itself is relevant to other researchers considering the use of semi-structured interviews as a methodology for qualitative research. The chosen methodology yielded a significant amount of information relevant to the topic of this research project, which helped to deepen the understanding of the supports teachers need to include a child with VI in primary PE lessons.

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